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Second Chance Education in Primary Education is very important in Bangladesh

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Abstract

Bangladesh is a densely populated country. There is no alternative but education is the tool to convert the masses to human resource. That's why government of Bangladesh wants to ensure the primary education in the early stages. Each child should be enrolled in school at the right time which is very important. Children who could not go to school in time for various reasons or dropped out later should be admitted into main stream by giving them Second Chance. Reality is that, the dropout rate from primary level is still noticeable and it must be addressed properly and that's why second chance education is very important in primary level in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Drop out, Enrollment, Main stream, Primary education, Second chance

Introduction

Bangladesh is an overpopulated country. This huge population is now a problem but it could be useful by converting them to human resource. Education is one of the basic tools to make them effective and more useful to the country. Education is the key to a nation's development. Considering the importance of education, Article 17 of our constitution clearly declares that the state should ensure "uniform, mass-oriented and universal" system of education for all. The importance of primary education in the national education and human life is considered to be the most important. Primary education creates the basis for all levels of education. If we want to establish our country as a prosperous developed country, we have to ensure cent percent of enrolment in primary level of education. In reality for many reasons it is not possible to enroll all the eligible children at the first chance that's mean in time so their need a second chance to get the scope of getting primary education.

Education policy

After many years effort we got an education policy in 2010 which spelled out the commitments and directions that education should take in the coming years [1]. It addressed both the fundamental philosophy of educational provision as well as some of its more detailed dimensions. With regard to understanding the policy basis for Second Chance Education (SCE), it is crucial to put SCE in the context of the commitments and intentions of the government. The policy addressed universal access, equitable opportunities, uniform curriculum, coordinated delivery and attention to dropout – all of which have a bearing on the provision of SCE.

Education System in Bangladesh

There are three education system in Bangladesh and those are:

- General Education system
- Madrasha Education system
- Technical-Vocational Education system

Each of these three system can be classified by three more levels, such as:

- Primary Level (Class 1-8) [2]
- Secondary Level (Class 9-12)
- Tertiary Level

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In every step of these system have dropout but it is very important to reduce dropout in primary level not only that have to be ensured of 100% enrollment in primary level. Dropout is a major factor in primary level [3] which should be addressed properly.

Cause of Dropout

A dropout can be defined as a child who enrolls in school but fails to complete the relevant level of the education cycle (Dropout Problems in Primary Education – Some Case Studies, UNESCO, 1984). According to Microsoft Encarta Encyclopedia 2002, a dropout is somebody who fails to complete an educational course, usually at a college or school. A dropout can also be termed as a pupil who was enrolled in the beginning of the school year and has left before the end of the school year, and was not enrolled elsewhere [4].

Many causes are there for dropout in primary level. Most of study on this regard showed that the major causes are

- Very poor households
- Most of the parents are illiterate, so they are unaware and do not understand the value of education
- Few earning members, so the earnings or the labor of the dropout are important for the survival of the family
- Poor performance in school
- Unsupportive school environment, etc.

Another cause besides those mentioned above is geographic location, which is very important in the case of drop out in primary level.

Present Situation

Although Bangladesh has achieved significant progress in primary education in terms of the enrollment of students and free distribution of books across the country, the present scenario of primary education in terms of enrollment is not 100% yet. Government is trying to address the problem properly.

Fig 1: Survival rate of grade 5 in different geographic location

Fig 2: Cycle dropout rate in different years

Enrolment in primary education in developing countries has reached 91 per cent but 57 million children remain out

of school [5]. Various studies shows that still the number of dropout children is quite noticeable in Bangladesh. Geographic location has an impact on drop out Fig. 1 shows the survival rate to Grade 5 in some different geographic locations [6]. Fig. 2 shows cycle (grade 1-5) completion dropout rate 2010-2014 in Bangladesh [7]. Above two figures clearly shows the existence of dropout in Bangladesh is quite remarkable which must be addressed by the second chance initiatives.

Government and Others Initiative

While the priority of the government of Bangladesh is to ensure that all children enroll in Primary School at an appropriate age, it is known that this is not always achieved for a number of reasons. Second Chance Education (SCE) acts as a safety net for children who do not enroll on time or do not complete their primary education. Through addressing the needs of children who have never enrolled in primary school, or who have dropped out of school, each child will be given a ‘second chance’ to learn. The Government’s commitment to SCE is reflected in its position as one of Primary Education Development Program 3 (PEDP-3)’s sub-components (sub-component 2.1.1 – Second Chance Education).

In August 2014 it was decided that Directorate of Primary Education (DPE) would adopt responsibility for implementing SCE [8]. The Government of Bangladesh has approved the creation of a new division named Second Chance & Alternative Education Division within DPE in order to support the achievement of these goals. The International Consultant is being engaged to support the process of reviewing and identifying model(s) and modalities considering the national international experiences and context.

At present government of Bangladesh is running a project named Out of School Children (ROSC) to give second chance education to the dropped out children with the help of the World Bank. It was started in 2005 (ROSC –I) and still going on (ROSC-II). ROSC II is built on the success of the first ROSC project that provided a second chance for primary education to nearly 780,000 poor children in 23,000 ROSC Learning Centers in 90 low-income upazillas. ROSC reintegrates out-of-school children into education through learning centers, called Ananda Schools (schools of joy), which provide education stipends to underprivileged children to lessen the burdens on their families as well as distribute free books, stationery and school uniforms. The Ananda Schools are established in upazilas with high poverty and low enrolment and completion rates. These schools blend formal education with a non-formal mode The schools run differently from normal primary schools: ROSC students tend to be older (between 8 and 14 years of age) than regular primary school students, students and teachers follow a flexible school timing to suit their mutual needs, and students are taught by a single class teacher, till they are ready to appear for the Grade-5 examination and can then join the mainstream secondary schools [9]. Beside that many NGO’s such as BRAC, Dhaka Ahsania Mission (DAM), TMSS, Save the children etc. along with the government is working on this issue. They are implementing their own program to reduce dropout in primary level.

BRAC

Over the past 29 years, the number of BRAC primary school has grown tremendously. BRAC started working in 1985, opening 22 one-room schools and providing three years of schooling up to class 3, which was extended to class 5 later. The main objective was to develop a school model for the underprivileged and primary school dropout children, especially girls, to complete the five-year primary school syllabus in four years. In 1991, BRAC launched Education Support Program (ESP) to enhance the access to quality primary education opportunities for underprivileged children (of 9-12 years) in the most remote areas including char (riverine islands), haor (wetlands), tea garden areas and the Chittagong Hill Tracts. ESP builds partnerships with local NGOs and provides them with technical and financial support to replicate BRAC's primary school (BPS) model. Thus, ESP supplements the government in achieving the goals of Education for All (EFA) in line with millennium development goals (MDGs) of education in Bangladesh. [10].

Dhaka Ahsania Mission

Dhaka Ahsania Mission (DAM) deliver education programs to reach children who are missing out on school. For example, DAM run one of the largest community education programs in Bangladesh, giving out-of-school children access to education in community centers and youth clubs. These children attend more classes and achieve higher grades than their peers in formal primary school. With UNICEF, DAM coordinate providing education to children during emergencies, ensuring that particularly vulnerable children don't miss out on the benefits that education brings.

Thengamara Mohila Sabuj Sangha (TMSS)

TMSS supported Ministry of Primary Education to implemented ROSC-I project and deployed necessary staffs to implement the project successfully. The main target of the project was to increase school enrollment, reduce in dropout rate, provide schooling for poor and disadvantaged households and children with disabilities due to various reasons. 78000 children were educated under 23000 learning centers known as Ananda School. They covered 90 upazila.

Save the Children

Save the Children is an international organization. It invests for the children for their better future. In the United States and around the world, Save the Children give children a healthy start, the opportunity to learn and protection from harm.

In Bangladesh Village Education and Resource Centre (VERC), a local partner of Save the Children established learning center in 2013 to provide second chance education. Through SHIKHON ("Learning") Program, Save the Children and implementing partners are providing cost-effective, quality, non-formal primary education (NFPE) to children from disadvantaged communities. European Union has been financially supporting SHIKHON and this model of reaching out children from disadvantaged communities has been acclaimed nationally.

All these initiatives follow the same national curriculum but way of approach is different.

At present in Bangladesh many activities have taken to reduce dropout and which have a positive impact on the retention rate in primary level, such as;

- Strengthening the admission process at the right time
- Reduce absenteeism rate
- Making the school environment attractive
- Make teaching interesting
- Preventing repetition
- Providing stipends
- System of Mid-Day Meal
- Provide free Education Materials
- Providing free School Dress for the Children from poor families
- Social mobilization on awareness of the necessity of Education among the local elites and parents.
- In fact GO-NGO collaboration is highly needed to reach the goal.

Conclusion

The system of providing primary education to the dropout children aged 6-14 should not consider non-formal rather it should be the formal and the way of approach may be different from regular formal education and it must be more flexible. In this process national curriculum must be followed. This way the importance and success of giving second chance education will be more fruitful. The objective of giving second chance in the primary level is to main stream to those who were not able to grab the first chance and have within the age limit of 6-14. Second chance education in primary level in Bangladesh is now demand of time and reality.

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